

TALENT DEVELOPMENT BASED ON TRAINING NEEDS ANALYSIS FOR EMPLOYEES OF LEARNING RESOURCES CENTRE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10810789>

Abstract. Talent development activities are crucial for employees to enhance their skills and improve their performance. This study was conducted to determine the training and development needs of employees at the Learning Resource Center of an international university in Tashkent. The findings showed that librarians need training on implementing electronic resource delivery services and using web 2.0 technology for effective service delivery. A special training program based on the needs analysis was developed and presented.

Keywords: staff training, training needs, learning resource centre library service delivery.

Annotatsiya. Iste'dodlarni rivojlantirish bo'yicha tadbirlar xodimlarning malakasini oshirish va ish faoliyatini yaxshilash uchun juda muhimdir. Ushbu tadqiqot Toshkent shahridagi xalqaro universitetning O'quv resurs markazi xodimlarini o'qitish va rivojlantirish ehtiyojlarini aniqlash maqsadida o'tkazildi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, kutubxonachilar elektron resurslarni yetkazib berish xizmatlarini joriy etish va samarali xizmat ko'rsatish uchun web 2.0 texnologiyasidan foydalanish bo'yicha treningga muhtoj. Ehtiyojlarni tahlil qilish asosida maxsus o'quv dasturi ishlab chiqildi va taqdim etildi.

Kalit so'zlar: xodimlarni tayyorlash, treyningga bo'lgan ehtiyoj, o'quv resurs markazi, kutubxona xizmatlari

Аннотация. Мероприятия по развитию талантов имеют решающее значение для сотрудников, позволяющих им совершенствовать свои навыки и повышать производительность. Данное исследование было проведено с целью определения потребностей в обучении и развитии сотрудников Центра учебных ресурсов международного университета в Ташкенте. Результаты показали, что библиотекарям необходимо обучение внедрению услуг по доставке электронных ресурсов и использованию технологии Web 2.0 для эффективного предоставления услуг. На основе анализа потребностей была разработана и представлена специальная программа обучения.

Ключевые слова: обучение персонала, потребности в обучении, учебный ресурсный центр, предоставление библиотечных услуг.

1.0 Introduction

The 21st century is a new era for the employment landscape because of the importance of absolute value as a competitive weapon (Ott, Tolentino, and Michaelova, 2018; Tlaiss, Martin, and Hofaidhllaoui, 2017). Organizations need to develop the capabilities and knowledge of current employees because it will help them not lose stability in different circumstances, and they should focus on the development of employees who will play important roles when the entities meet future challenges (CIPD, 2009). Moreover, it is critical to evaluate learning to determine its efficacy in delivering the results indicated when the activity was designed, as well as to identify where enhancements or modifications are needed to make the training even more effective (Armstrong, 2014). According to Dessler (2013), a variety of things can be measured while evaluating the programs, including Participants' reactions to the program, what (if anything) the trainees learned from it, and how much their on-the-job behavior or outcomes changed due to the program. The survey among 500 U.S. organizations showed that 77% assessed their training programs by

eliciting the reaction, 36% measured learning, and 10% to 15% examined the program’s conduct and/or outcomes (Wexley and Latham, 2002).

2.0 Literature Review

University Learning Research Centres play crucial role because it makes obtainable and reachable information in distinguish format to maintain the teaching, learning and research objectives of the institution of learning process (Onah, Adayi, Okonkwo and Onyebuchi, 2020). Training needs analysis helps to libraries’ staff to find out needs to perform job better and show full performance to achieve mission of organization (Anyaegbu and Wali, 2019). The Learning Research Centre employees need to obtain distinguish skills such as online repository among others, online navigation skills and social media use skills (Rafiq, Batool, Ali and Ullah, 2020). Iwuchukwu and Echedon (2020) stated that in-house trainings, seminars, workshops, conferences, job rotation as well as formal professional library education through others are the effective methods for acquiring new skills. Training of employees develop competencies (Okemwa,2000), decrease the level of deficiencies (Goldstein, 2002), assisting to obtain innovative knowledges and improve professional growth (Ford and Kraiger, 1995). According to Nazli (2014) the success or failure of training depends on selection of right employee for the program. Moreover, Miller and Osinski (1996) provided three level of TNA:

-Organizational analysis: Focusing on organizational objectives, number of staff, performance evaluation reports and environmental scanning.

- Task analysis: Providing information on required skills for job description, model of competency, performance evaluation standards and job structures.

-Individual analysis: Evaluating TNA based on workers’ performance, attitude as well as observation.

3.0 Methods

The interview type of data collection method was used to identify training needs in the organization. To make proper analysis structured type of interviews were conducted. To ensure the collection of accurate and relevant information for our interview, we have contacted members of the Learning Resources Centre team from an international university in Tashkent.

4.0 Results

4.1 Shortage in Training and Development Programs at the University

The results of the interviews with the selected staff proved that there are some shortcomings in terms of talent development in the organizational process. Universities should provide additional learning and development opportunities to retain top talent and boost employee satisfaction with their work. A training needs survey for newcomers is also necessary to speed up their transition into the workplace. Stringer (2020) confirmed that nearly 94% of employees want to stay with the company longer if they can take advantage of learning and development opportunities to help them reach their full potential.

4.2 Interview with employees working Learning Resource Centre

The interview, which was conducted to analyse the needs for learning and development, was with the members of the Learning Resources Centre team. They stated that one of the main duty stays in front of higher education sectors is to achieve students’ satisfaction or retain the satisfaction level if it is already attained. According to them, university LRC is the place where students can easily find reliable and credible resources related to their studying area. LRC of the university provided mostly hard copies of the books before the COVID–19 pandemic situations. When the virus of COVID–19 was detected in Uzbekistan, there were sudden lockdowns, students

were not able to enter the campus and the demand for electronic books increased sharply. The rector of the institute assigned the task of creating a new electronic library immediately. At that time working with IT staff was even harder, as all the departments worked at a distance and they approached the IT department when problems occurred with LMS, Zoom sessions, etc. LRC manager said that he provided all the PDF versions of the books in high demand to place to the new system. They solved the problem a bit, but they needed enough time to create a new system that would cover all LRC processes, such as booking, searching for books, checking for electronic versions of books, being aware of return dates, and so on, according to the manager.

Recently, a new digital library has been launched where students can easily access electronic versions of the books. The LRC manager indicated that he should make a presentation on how to utilize the digital library to his assistants and specialists. However, he does not have enough knowledge about using the system effectively. For this reason, it will be a great opportunity for him, if the training session is conducted on implementation and efficient usage of the system.

5.0 Discussion and Recommendation

According to Armstrong (2014), effective training is a systematic method that emphasizes skills analysis. The aim of the training should be specified in terms of the behaviour that is expected to occur due to the training session. The development of transferrable abilities should be the primary goal of training. The training should be assessed based on how well it accomplished its objectives.

The process of developing a training program is much more complex than simply contracting with an online training vendor and asking your staff to complete the course (Dessler, 2013). The company should implement a logical training approach. The basic analysis-design-development-implement-evaluate (ADDIE) training process approach, which has been utilized by training specialists for many years, remains the gold standard in this field (Allen, 2006). According to the ADDIE model of training approach, the next step is designing and developing the proper training program. Based on the obtained information from the interviews, it is intended to carry out training and development activities for employees working at LRC.

5.1 Training session on using electronic library

The training that is intended to be held is on how to utilize the newly launched electronic library (digital library). The manager of LRC stressed that the training should be for all his employees since students often approach library staff if they face difficulties using the system.

The classroom type has been selected to make a training session. This training session includes lectures and audio-visual-based training programs. Moreover, in this training session, learners will be allowed to use the platform and ask questions if something is unclear. There is a PC lab inside the campus, which helps to handle layout-related issues. The reason for choosing the PC lab room is that the platform requires access to the internet via computers.

One of the program developers of the digital library has been selected as a trainer for the training session. On Saturday, all the specialists, assistant managers, and the manager of LRC will be invited to the training session and it will be mandatory for them. The reason for choosing Saturday for the session is that this day is not a working day. One week before the training session, an invitation letter will be sent to the learners indicating the time, venue, and purpose of the session by webmail (internal way of communication).

Following are the set of activities that are going to be delivered by the trainer during the session:

- Welcoming speech

- Lecture about the platform (using PPT slides) – according to Dessler (2013), lecturing is a quick and easy approach to impart knowledge to large groups of learners.
- Video lesson on how to use the digital library (the video will be prepared before the session and will be sent via webmail after the training session)
- Practicing the usage of the platform
- Question and Answer session
- Training session is expected to last two to three hours, depending on the question and answer session period.

6.0 Conclusion

Training plans can improve not only the effectiveness, efficiency, or skills of employees but also serve as tools to develop organizational performance and productivity. Employers may ensure that their workforce has the necessary abilities and expertise to accomplish job duties effectively by focusing on talent development procedures, which is advanced by relying on employee skill gaps analysis. Thus, it is essential to design appropriate training and development procedures and implement them to enhance employees' professionalism in the accomplishment of their assigned duties and future growth.

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